

Synthesis of Some Newer 3-Substituted-4(3H) Quinazolones-Part II

D. D. MUKERJI and (Miss) S. R. NAUTIYAL

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow

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Sixteen 3(2'-arylimino-4-oxo-thiazolin-3-yl) methyl quinazolones have been synthesized with a view to study their psychotropic properties.

THE wide variety of CNS depressant¹ properties including anaesthetic², anti-convulsant³ and sedative⁴ activity are associated with thiazolidone derivatives, whereas anti-convulsant and hypnotic activity of 4-quinazolones have been reported by several authors⁵⁻⁹. These observations prompted us to synthesize a large number of 4(3H)quinazolones incorporating thiazolidone moiety.

3(2'-arylimino-4-oxo-thiazolin-3-yl)methyl quinazolones(III) were synthesized by condensing 3-amino-methyl-4(3H)quinazolones(I), with various aryl isothiocyanates under different reaction conditions to give their corresponding 3-substituted unsymmetrical thioureas(II)

(recorded in Table 1) which were characterized by their elemental, I.R. and N.M.R. analyses. The presence

of characteristic bonds at 1642 cm^{-1} for $\begin{array}{c} \text{N} \\ | \\ \text{C} \\ || \\ \text{O} \end{array}$ and at 1490 cm^{-1} for $\begin{array}{c} \text{N} \\ | \\ \text{C} \\ || \\ \text{S} \end{array}$ grouping provided support

for their structures. These thioureas on cyclization yielded 3(2'-arylimino-4-oxo-thiazolin-3-yl)methyl quinazolones(III). The parent thiocarbamides show thiocarbonyl absorption around 1230 cm^{-1} . Lack of this absorption after cyclization confirms the formation of a thiazolidone ring. The bands at $820-865\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $740-755\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the presence of *o*-disubstituted phenyl and mono substituted phenyl groups. In the N.M.R. spectrum a singlet due to methylene protons was observed at δ 2.40. Signal for N-CH₂-N was observed at δ 4.12. A multiplet at δ 6.80-7.7 has been assigned to aromatic protons. The elemental analyses of all these compounds also agree with the assigned structures.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in a sulphuric acid bath in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer in KBr. N.M.R. spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer R32 90 MHz N.M.R. instruments in DMSO-d₆ as solvent and with Me₄Si as an internal standard. T.L.C. was carried out on Kieselgel G coated glass plates of 2 m.m. thickness.

N-Aryl-*N'*-(4(3H)quinazolone-3-yl) methyl thiourea(II) :

A mixture of 3-aminomethyl 4(3H) quinazolone(I) (0.01 M) and a suitable aryl iso-thiocyanate (0.01M) in 15 ml of dry benzene was refluxed for 3-4 hours. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure. On cooling the solid mass which separated out, was filtered, washed with ether and dilute HCl; and recrystallized from ethanol and are recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—N-ARYL-N'-(4(3H) QUINAZOLONE-3-YL) METHYL THIOUREAS (II)

S. No.	Ar	R ₁	R ₂	M. P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis %					
						Carbon		Nitrogen		Hydrogen	
						Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	H	H	166-168	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ OS2HCl	49.97	50.13	14.51	14.62	4.11	4.20
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	H	212-213	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS2HCl	51.26	51.38	14.03	14.11	4.39	4.53
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	H	192-193	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS2HCl	51.22	51.38	11.09	14.11	4.44	4.53
4.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	H	174-175	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S2HCl	49.19	49.39	13.48	13.56	4.28	4.36
5.	phenyl	H	Br	Above 290	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ BrOS ..	41.42	41.56	12.04	12.12	3.15	3.24
6.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	Br	Above 290	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ BrOS ..	42.69	42.86	11.67	11.76	3.39	3.57
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	Br	285-287	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ BrOS ..	42.63	42.86	11.72	11.76	3.34	3.57
8.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	Br	238-239	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ BrO ₂ S ..	41.28	47.47	11.29	11.38	3.35	3.46
9.	Phenyl	Br	Br	Above 290	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ Br ₂ OS ..	35.38	35.49	10.31	10.35	2.41	2.58
10.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Br	Br	252-253	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ Br ₂ OS.2HCl	36.61	36.78	10.14	10.09	2.72	2.80
11.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Br	Br	Above 290 (d 280)	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ Br ₂ OS.2HCl	36.67	36.78	10.11	10.09	2.69	2.88
12.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Br	Br	Above 290	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ Br ₂ O ₂ S.2HCl	35.81	35.73	9.71	9.87	2.62	2.80
13.	phenyl	H	NO ₂	Above 290	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ S.2HCl	44.62	44.86	16.21	16.35	3.37	3.50
14.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	NO ₂	260-261	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S.2HCl	46.08	46.17	15.68	15.84	3.65	3.85
15.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	NO ₂	Above 290	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S.2HCl	46.11	46.17	15.63	15.84	3.58	3.85
16.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	NO ₂	281-282	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S.2HCl	44.38	44.54	15.12	15.27	3.02	3.17

(i) All the compounds were obtained in 60-70% yield.

TABLE 2-3 (2'-ARYLIMINO-4-OXO-THIAZOLIN-3-YL) METHYL QUINAZOLONES (III)

Sl. No.	Ar	R ₁	R ₂	M. P. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis of Nitrogen %	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	Phenyl	H	H	132-133	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S.HCl	14.44	14.51
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	H	121-122	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S.HCl	13.97	14.00
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	H	164-165	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S.HCl	13.93	14.00
4.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	H	223-224	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S.HCl	13.29	13.45
5.	Phenyl	H	Br	206-207	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ BrS.HCl	11.96	12.04
6.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	Br	242-243	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ BrS.HCl	11.51	11.69
7.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	Br	266-268	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ BrS.HCl	11.56	11.69
8.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	Br	254-256	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ BrS.HCl	11.23	11.31
9.	Phenyl	Br	Br	Above 290 (d 260)	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ Br ₂ S.HCl	10.16	10.29
10.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Br	Br	226	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ Br ₂ S.HCl	9.97	10.04
11.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Br	Br	274	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ Br ₂ S.HCl	9.92	10.04
12.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Br	Br	292 (d)	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ Br ₂ S.HCl	9.61	9.76
13.	Phenyl	H	NO ₂	274	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₃ S.HCl	16.11	16.23
14.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	NO ₂	212	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S.HCl	15.63	15.71
15.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	NO ₂	192	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S.HCl	15.58	15.71
16.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	H	NO ₂	202	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ S.HCl	15.09	15.17

(i) All the compounds were obtained in 60-80% yield.

3(2'-arylimino-4-oxo-thiazolin-3-yl) methyl quinazolones(III) :

N-Aryl-N'-4(3H)quinazolon-3-yl methyl thiourea(II) (0.01 mole) monochloroacetic acid (0.01 mole) and fused sodium acetate (0.01 mole) were mixed in 15 ml glacial acetic acid and the mixture was refluxed on a free flame for 5 to 6 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and kept over night at 0°. The crude product which separated out on cooling was filtered, washed several times with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol and are recorded in the Table 2.

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